

JUPITER MERCURY

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Abstract:

Jupiter is the planet for money and Mercury is the planet for knowledge. Both the above planets make one an expert. The particular field is chosen by other planets which has conjunction with Jupiter and Mercury. Money is essential for our survival. Knowledge is also essential for our survival. Without money we can't live. Without knowledge we can't live.

Key Words: Astrology – Science – Saints – Eternal Power – Guidance – Rule for MBA – Higher Education – Expert in Music Expert in Astrology – Tamil Vidwan – Richest Poet – Expert in Maths – Expert in Art – Expert in Speech – Expert In Dance – Expert in Poison Sastra

Introduction:

Jupiter and Mercury play a vital role in our horoscope. If they are strength they will help us to improve our name and fame. So, we must understand the importance of Jupiter and Mercury.

Astrology is greater than Science:

Science has only formula and logic. But astrology has formula, logic and intuition power. So, astrology is greater than Science.

Saints Who Developed Astrology:

Sun, Bhrammadeva, Naratha, Vashishta, Karki, Parasara, Veda Vyasa, Athri, Patha rayana, Chanakya, Uroma, Pulisha, Kashyaba, Manu, Poulaga, Chyavana Bhirugu, Angirasa, Varahamihira, Mandreswar helped to develop astrology.

Eternal Power is Astrology:

Not only poor people but also the richest people suffer a lot. When they faced failures they trusted on astrology. Astrology is an eternal power.

Guidance for Higher Education:

Now a days there are more than 3000 courses in higher education So, guidance and counselling is must for students to choose their careers.

Who Can Study MBA:

In whose horoscope Jupiter and Mercury connects with 4/5/9/10 bhavas one could study MBA easily.

I. Jupiter and Mercury Make One an Expert in Higher Education:

- Jupiter, Mercury and Second Lord stand in kendra (1/4/7/10) or trine (1/5/9) the native will study higher education easily.
- If Jupiter stands in eleventh bhava and aspects Mercury and Moon, the native will study higher education easily.
- If Jupiter stands in 1/5/9/11 bhava the native will study higher education easily.

II. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Music:

- If the second lord conjunctions with Jupier and stands in good bhavas and aspected by Venus the native will be an expert in music.
- If the second lord is Venus and aspected by Jupiter the native will be an expert in music.

III. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Astrology:

- If the second lord stands in 1/4/7/10 (Kendra) with Mercury or aspected by Mercury the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If Jupiter stands in 1/4/7/10 (kendra) or 1/5/9 Trine the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If the second lord is Sun or Mars and aspected by Jupiter the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If Mercury stands in 1/4/7/10 (kendra) and the second lord gets exhaltation, the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If Jupiter stands in 1/4/7/10 (kendra) and Venus gets exhaltation, the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If Sun or Mars stands in second bhava and aspected by Jupier, the native will be an expert in astrology.
- If Jupiter becomes second lord and aspected by Sun and Venus, the native will be an expert in astrology.

IV. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Tamil Language:

- If Mercury stands in 1/4/7/10 (kendra) or 1/5/9 (Trine), the native will be an expert in Tamil language.
- If Mercury stands in Second bhava, the native will be an expert in Tamil language.

- If Jupiter stands in lagna or Mars stands in 1/5/9 (Trine), the native will be an expert in Tamil language.

V. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Telugu Language:

- If Mars stands in 1/4/7/10 (kendra) or 1/5/9 (Trine), the native will be an expert in Telugu language.
- If Mars stands in Second bhava, the native will be an expert in Telugu language.
- If Jupiter stands in lagna or Mars stands in 1/5/9 (Trine), the native will be an expert in Telugu language.

VI. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Poetry:

- If Jupiter conjunctions with Mercury and Sun in lagna the native will be an expert in poetry.

VII. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Maths:

- If Jupiter in lagna, Saturn in eighth bhava and both Mercury and Second Lord get exaltation, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If Mars in Second bhava and aspected by Mercury and Moon, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If the exaltation Mercury is a second Lord and Jupiter stands in lagna on sixth or eighth bhava, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If Mercury stands twelfth bhava from Sun, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If Mercury conjunctions with Venus and Saturn, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If Mercury stands in Gemini or Virgo and that bhava is 1/4/7/10 (Kendra) or 1/5/9 (Trine), Jupiter and Mars conjunction in any bhava, the native will be an expert in maths.
- If Jupiter stands in 1/4/7/10 Kendra or 1/5/9 (Trine), Mercury stands in second bhava and Venus gets exaltation, the native will be an expert in maths.

VIII. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Arts:

- If Mercury conjunctions with Jupiter or Moon, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Mercury conjunction with Sun in second bhava and aspected by Jupiter, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Mercury conjunctions with Sun and Venus in second bhava, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Mercury in eleventh bhava, Jupiter in tenth bhava and Moon in second bhava, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Jupiter, Mercury and Venus conjunction in second bhava, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Jupiter, Mercury and Moon stands in Virgo lagna, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Jupiter stands in Virgo lagna and Mercury stands in Sagittarius, the native will be an expert in arts.
- If Mercury conjunctions with Mars in tenth bhava, the native will be an expert in arts.

IX. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Speech:

- If Mercury stands in lagna and aspected by lagna lord, the native will be an expert in speech.
- If Mercury conjunctions with second lord and stands in fourth bhava, the native will be an expert in speech.
- If Mercury conjunctions with Moon and Venus and aspected by Jupiter, the native will be an expert in speech.
- If Jupiter, Mercury and Venus conjunction in ninth bhava, the native will be an expert in speech.
- If Jupiter, Mercury, Moon and Mars conjunction in tenth bhava, the native will be an expert in speech.
- If Mercury and Venus conjunction with lagna lord, the native will be an expert in speech.

X. Jupiter & Mercury Make One an Expert in Dance:

- If Mercury, Jupiter and Mars stand in fourth bhava the native will be an expert in dance.
- If Venus conjunctions with twelfth Lord in tenth house and Mercury stands in Gemini or Virgo, the native will be an expert in dance.

Conclusion:

If we want to be an expert in any field we should strengthen Jupiter and Mercury. One should worship Tiruchendur Jayanthi Nathar to develop the strength of Jupiter. One should worship Madurai Chokkanathar to develop the strength of Mercury.

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